

Advancing Media Literacy & Digital Skills Interventions: Recommendations for Stakeholders

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Executive summary

This report supports policymakers, educators, NGOs, civil society organisations, and intervention designers in strengthening their media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) initiatives through evidence-based insights and practical guidance. It presents a synthesis of findings and recommendations from the REMEDIS (Rethinking Media Literacy and Digital Skills) project.

What we learned

The findings show that well-designed interventions can significantly improve ML&DS, but they also highlight persistent challenges and gaps in reach, depth, and sustainability.

- Interventions were most effective when they were **sustained over time**, adapted to the specific needs of target groups, and responsive to local contexts.
- A common challenge across all groups was **low participation**, which limited programme reach and made long-term evaluation more difficult.
- Trainer engagement, local relevance, and iterative programme development emerged as **key factors for success**, especially for underserved groups.

What we need

Improving the effectiveness and impact of ML&DS interventions requires coordinated, multi-level action from all stakeholders.

- **Policymakers** should provide stable, long-term funding and integrate ML&DS into national strategies across education, employment, and inclusion.
- **Educators** need regular, targeted training and support to integrate digital literacy into everyday teaching.
- **NGOs and civil society organisations** must align programmes with community needs, ensure accessibility, and plan for long-term sustainability.
- **Designers and evaluators** should use theory-driven, evidence-based frameworks and embed evaluation from the start, including long-term follow-up.

How to move forward

To strengthen ML&DS interventions across Europe, stakeholders need access to practical tools, collaborative partnerships, and shared learning.

- The **REMEDIS Evaluation Toolkit** and **AI-powered Evaluation Planner** offer step-by-step guidance to help design, assess, and scale effective, inclusive, and sustainable practices.
- Collaboration between sectors, including schools, governments, researchers, and NGOs, enhances relevance, reach, and quality.
- Sharing successful strategies, tools, and insights enables others to adapt and improve interventions in their own contexts.

Introduction

The REMEDIS project

The REMEDIS project is funded by the European Union's CHANSE (Collaboration of Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe) programme. The consortium involves 7 academic partners from 6 countries and 14 non-academic cooperation partners. Within these countries, REMEDIS pays special attention to target groups, including youths Not in Education, Employment, or Training (NEETs), the unemployed, refugees, lower SES people, elderly, NEET carers and (future) teachers.

REMEDIS aims to understand the positive impacts of Media Literacy and Digital Skills (ML&DS) interventions across different life domains. To achieve this, REMEDIS adopts innovative, evidence-based research strategies that first aims to identify and quantify the most salient driving factors for ML&DS from a lifelong perspective. The project then develops and evaluates initiatives that foster ML&DS.

The REMEDIS project has four core research objectives:

1. To improve existing theoretical knowledge about the actual outcomes of interventions.
2. To improve and enhance existing ML&DS intervention strategies based on existing and emerging evidence.
3. Adopt advanced methods and develop and validate instruments for evaluating intervention strategies.
4. To produce evidence-based policy recommendations and develop a user-friendly, customisable evaluation toolkit and an AI-powered evaluation guide.

This report advances objective 4 by synthesising the project's findings and formulating evidence-based recommendations for stakeholders, including policymakers.

This report

This report serves as a key output of the REMEDIS project and relates to its fourth core objective: to produce evidence-based policy recommendations. Drawing on the findings of a systematic literature review, twelve evaluation studies conducted across six European countries, and close collaboration with practitioners, policymakers, and community stakeholders, this report translates research insights into practical guidance.

The primary aim is to support stakeholders, including policymakers, educators, NGOs, civil society organisations, and intervention designers, in designing, implementing, and evaluating effective ML&DS initiatives. The report synthesises the evidence gathered by the REMEDIS consortium to identify what works, what doesn't, and why, with a particular focus on inclusivity, sustainability, and real-world impact.

Key findings

What worked and what didn't?

Effective intervention strategies

Based on a systematic evidence review of the available literature on ML&DS intervention evaluations, as well as empirical evaluation studies of twelve ML&DS interventions, the project has shown that certain approaches in intervention design can lead to better outcomes.

Overall, well-resourced, thoughtfully designed interventions, characterised by participant-centred design, skilled instruction, and grounded in evidence-based methods, seemed most effective in enhancing participants' ML&DS competencies.

Effective intervention strategies leading to better outcomes included:

- **Participant-centred design:** Tailored content to learners' needs and contexts proved more effective.
- **Active participant engagement:** Interactive, peer-to-peer, and scenario-based learning improved outcomes.
- **Well-trained facilitators:** Skilled, patient instructors were crucial to success, especially with older adults.
- **Relevance:** Interventions that were designed for a specific community or group tended to better hold participants' interest and could yield stronger skill or knowledge gains.
- **Robust intervention design,** with longer interventions, using diverse teaching methods (e.g., combining workshops, group discussion, hands-on practice) and input from external experts saw more positive and sustained outcomes.
- **Evaluation plan:** The presence of robust and iterative evaluation methods contributed to stronger evidence of impact. Sustaining impact through iterative programme development and the ability to adapt and respond to participants' feedback enhance both engagement with and efficacy of the intervention.
- **Theory-driven interventions** were more effective because they had clearer logic, better alignment with intended outcomes, and measurable impact. Using established frameworks (e.g. theory of planned behaviour, social cognitive theory) ensured that interventions addressed not just knowledge, but also attitudes and behaviours, leading to deeper and more lasting improvements in media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS).
- **Continuous support:** Iterative development, participant feedback, and follow-up activities helped sustain impact.
- **Collaborative approach:** Multi-stakeholder coordination enhanced programme reach and quality.

Common challenges that limit the efficacy of ML&DS intervention include issues related to digital divides, language barriers, as well as programme design oversights such as overlooking individual learning differences, or relying on “one-size-fits-all” content and strategies.

Common challenges and barriers that inhibited positive outcomes of interventions included:

- **One-size-fits-all content:** Ignored diverse starting points and limited effectiveness.
- **Low participation and retention:** Many interventions faced low participation and retention, limiting their impact and generalizability. To address this, programs need better outreach and retention strategies, along with evaluation methods suited to smaller sample sizes.
- **Access issues and technical difficulties** such as poor internet access, outdated devices, and technical issues hindered participant engagement, especially among disadvantaged groups. Ignoring individual learners’ needs further reduced intervention effectiveness.
- **Underestimating learner diversity:** Differences in language, literacy, and learning pace led to some participants falling behind. Simplified or translated content and tailored support are essential, but often missing. Effective interventions require long-term, inclusive strategies that address these diverse needs from the outset.
- **Short-term interventions:** while basic digital skills can be boosted relatively quickly, deeper critical digital literacy (such as recognising disinformation tactics) requires more extensive training.

Intervention outcomes

Intervention outcomes were influenced not just by design but also by broader contextual factors like policy, culture, and the types of organisations in charge of implementation. Successful interventions often involved strong coordination among stakeholders, including schools, community groups, civil society, and policymakers.

In general, we found that:

Tailored, sustained approaches work best: Long-term, tailored training is more effective than short, uniform sessions across all groups.

Advanced skills need deeper support: Building critical digital literacy requires more time and integration into daily learning or routines.

Context and coordination matter: Strong outcomes depended on collaboration among stakeholders and sensitivity to local needs.

The following sections outline specific outcomes by target group, highlighting what worked, where challenges remained, and how different audiences responded to intervention efforts.

Outcomes for parents

- Digital parenting workshops helped many parents feel **more confident** managing their children's online activities, especially around safety, social media use, and cyberbullying.
- Parents became **more comfortable** setting rules, using parental controls, and talking with their children about internet use.
- However, many still **struggled with advanced digital skills** like spotting misinformation and critically evaluating online content, which are areas that short workshops didn't adequately cover.
- To fully empower parents, programs need to **go beyond the basics** and include more in-depth training on critical digital literacy.
- Most participants were mothers, highlighting the **need for better outreach to fathers** and more gender-balanced engagement.

Outcomes for youth

- Programs for young people showed **modest but positive results**, particularly in helping secondary and vocational students better recognize digital influence, such as spotting bias in news or identifying influencer marketing.
- These **gains in critical thinking** suggest even short-term efforts can boost awareness of online risks and persuasion tactics.
- However, **improvements in broader digital knowledge and skills were limited**, with only slight increases in general digital know-how and information literacy.
- **Short, one-off sessions are not enough**. Deeper learning requires more sustained and immersive approaches.
- A key recommendation is to **integrate media literacy into the regular school curriculum**, ensuring students build and reinforce digital skills over time through repeated exposure.

Outcomes for educators

- Training programs for teachers **boosted confidence in using digital tools** and evaluating online content, which significantly improved their digital skills and classroom practices.
- Interventions in which educators learned to create more interactive, media-rich lessons using apps and online resources, **enhanced student engagement and collaboration**.
- Teachers also valued **peer networking** and sharing best practices, which supported ongoing collaboration beyond the initial training.
- However, a **one-size-fits-all approach didn't work for everyone**. Teachers started at different skill levels, and some felt either overwhelmed or under-challenged.
- Programs that adapted to **individual needs** (e.g., through assessments or modular content) were more effective.
- **Continued professional development** is essential, and single workshops aren't enough to sustain digital competence in teaching.

Outcomes for the elderly

- Digital training for seniors, including computer and smartphone workshops, led to clear **gains in basic skills** like using email, messaging apps, online services, and adjusting privacy settings.
- These improvements **boosted participants' confidence**, independence, and sense of security in handling everyday digital tasks such as online banking or video calls.
- **More complex areas** like social media use and spotting misinformation remained challenging, even after training. In general, however, seniors responded well to topics like AI and deepfakes when **presented clearly and accessibly**.
- The most effective programs used **hands-on, step-by-step instruction** with slow pacing, repeated demonstrations, and a supportive, low-pressure environment.
- Success was strongly tied to the presence of **well-trained, patient instructors and adequate support**, including one-on-one help and bilingual or volunteer assistants when needed.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, we provide practical, action-focused recommendations for key stakeholder groups to strengthen the impact and sustainability of ML&DS interventions.

Recommendations for policymakers

- **Provide stable, long-term funding:** Short-term funding and project-based grants limit programme continuity and development. Sustainable financing through government budgets or public-private partnerships enables interventions to mature, evolve, and reach disadvantaged groups. Integration into broader education, employment, or inclusion initiatives helps ensure ongoing support.
- **Integrate ML&DS into national curricula and lifelong learning:** Embedding ML&DS into formal and adult education leads to more consistent engagement and better learning outcomes. This includes updating education guidelines to address online safety, misinformation, artificial intelligence, and digital citizenship across subjects, and ensuring that teacher training and resources are in place to support this integration.
- **Require robust evaluation, including follow-ups:** Many interventions lack long-term evaluation, making it hard to assess sustained outcomes. Policymakers should mandate sound evaluation frameworks with indicators, pre/post assessments, and follow-up studies to track lasting impacts on digital inclusion and wellbeing. Evaluation should be built into funding requirements and support cross-programme comparisons.
- **Promote knowledge sharing and collaboration:** Open sharing of toolkits, case studies, and evaluation instruments accelerates improvement across the ML&DS ecosystem. Policymakers should support platforms for best practice exchange, national forums, and practitioner networks, and invest in the rollout of standardised tools to schools, libraries, and NGOs.
- **Address digital inequality and access barriers:** Structural barriers such as poor internet access, lack of devices, and limited support for minority languages reduce participation. Policies should invest in broadband infrastructure, device lending schemes, and

accessible content, and require materials to be provided in multiple languages and formats to ensure inclusion.

Recommendations for educators and trainers

- **Engage in regular, tailored training:** One-time workshops are not sufficient. Teachers who participate in ongoing, adaptable professional development are better able to integrate ML&DS into their classrooms. Institutions should create a culture of continuous learning and peer mentoring, using subject-specific training and certified courses or online webinars.
- **Integrate ML&DS across everyday teaching:** When ML&DS is embedded into existing lessons, like using news in language classes or analysing propaganda in history, students engage more deeply. Teachers should use current, real-world examples and map digital literacy goals to curriculum standards for better alignment.
- **Use inclusive strategies to support diverse learners:** Students vary in digital experience and access. Educators should provide extra lab time, offer peer support, and adjust content to meet the needs of learners with limited access, learning difficulties, or language barriers. Creating a low-pressure environment encourages participation and skill development.
- **Collaborate with peers to improve practice:** Teacher networks promote shared learning and problem-solving. Educators who connect across schools report increased confidence and innovation in digital teaching. Time and platforms for regular collaboration, like school meetups or online forums, can drive consistency and ongoing improvement.

Recommendations for NGOs and civil society organisations

- **Conduct community needs assessments:** Interventions work best when shaped by the concerns and conditions of the community. Needs assessments through surveys, focus groups, or informal conversations help tailor content to what matters.
- **Partner with trusted local figures to boost participation:** Collaborating with respected community leaders like librarians, teachers, or past participants builds trust and improves outreach. These figures can co-deliver sessions or promote them through familiar channels, increasing credibility and turnout.
- **Design sessions to be accessible and flexible:** Successful interventions use slower pacing, repeated demonstrations, and hands-on practice. Materials should be translated and presented clearly. Sessions should be held in convenient locations and scheduled around participant availability, for example, evenings or weekends for working adults.
- **Plan for long-term sustainability:** To avoid programme collapse after funding ends, organisations should build in sustainability from the start. This includes training local facilitators, embedding sessions in partner institutions like schools or libraries, and creating reusable materials such as manuals or digital content that can live on in public repositories.

Recommendations for intervention designers and evaluators

- **Base interventions on clear goals and evidence-based frameworks:** Interventions that follow a theoretical model show more consistent results. Setting clear outcomes (e.g., safer online behaviour or improved critical thinking) ensures all content and activities align toward measurable goals.
- **Build evaluation into programme design from the start:** Evaluation is more effective when planned from the beginning. This includes identifying indicators, selecting validated tools, and piloting instruments with the target group. Trainers should be informed of evaluation goals so they understand the process and can support data collection effectively.
- **Use tailored evaluation tools for different groups:** A one-size-fits-all approach doesn't work. Youth may respond better to gamified quizzes, while adults may prefer surveys or practical demonstrations. Low-literacy participants may need visual tools or oral formats. Cultural differences and secondary outcomes like confidence or motivation should also be considered.
- **Track long-term outcomes through follow-up:** Development of ML&DS is a long-term process. Evaluators should follow up months after the programme to assess whether skills are retained. This can involve short surveys or refresher sessions. Collecting multiple contact methods and working with community partners helps reduce participant drop-off.
- **Use the REMEDIS Toolkit and Evaluation Planner:** The REMEDIS Evaluation Toolkit and Evaluation Planner provide a step-by-step guide to intervention planning and evaluation, including needs analysis, design, measurement, and reporting. They help ensure consistent, rigorous evaluation and promote collaboration with academic partners for deeper insight.

In general, our recommendations can then be summarized as follows:

Ensure long-term investment: Move beyond short-term projects by securing sustained funding and embedding ML&DS into education and inclusion policies.

Adapt to audience needs: Design interventions that reflect the specific skills, contexts, and goals of different groups.

Integrate ML&DS into everyday learning: Embed ML&DS across school subjects, adult education, and community programmes using real-life content.

Support educators and facilitators: Provide ongoing training, peer collaboration, and adaptable resources to those delivering ML&DS interventions.

Embed evaluation from the start: Plan for simple, audience-appropriate evaluation and follow-up to measure both immediate and long-term impact.

Promote collaboration and knowledge sharing: Share tools, strategies, and lessons learned through open-access resources and cross-sector networks.

Conclusion

The REMEDIS project demonstrates that **ML&DS interventions can have a meaningful and lasting impact** on individuals and communities. From boosting everyday digital confidence to enabling safer online behaviour, critical thinking, and civic participation, these interventions are essential tools for navigating today's complex digital landscape. As they are embedded within **broader systems of support**, they must be designed with the needs of their target groups in mind, aligned with local realities, and supported by enabling policies and infrastructure.

To create sustainable change, ML&DS initiatives must be **inclusive, adaptable, and sustained over time**. This requires coordinated, long-term investment; cross-sector collaboration between educators, policymakers, civil society, and researchers; and a shared commitment to ongoing learning, evaluation, and improvement. Persistent challenges such as digital access barriers, low participation rates, and gaps in advanced digital competencies must be addressed head-on, especially for those most at risk of digital exclusion.

The **REMEDIS Evaluation Toolkit and AI-powered Evaluation Planner** provide practical, evidence-based support to help stakeholders design, implement, and assess effective interventions. These tools function as stepping stones toward more resilient, equitable, and scalable ML&DS ecosystems.

Moving forward, success will depend on how well we turn knowledge into action, by embedding ML&DS into mainstream education, community programmes, and lifelong learning strategies; by working together across sectors; and by sharing what works so others can build on it.

Other REMEDIS reports

Are you interested in learning more about the REMEDIS project and the findings? Visit our website <https://remedis-chanse.eu/> to learn more about the project.

Previously published reports from the REMEDIS project:

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